

Support Vectors vs. Sensory Defects: Competing in the CAC2026 Chemometric Data Challenge

Stephan Freitag

Institute of Bioanalytics and Agro-Metabolomics, BOKU-University

Stephan.Freitag@boku.ac.at

Motivation

During the Chemometrics in Analytical Chemistry Conference (CAC) a chemometrics data challenge was organized, with the aim to develop a predictive model to classify olive oil according to musty defects.¹ The shared real olive oil data set was chemically characterized by head-space mass spectrometry (HS-MS), attenuated total reflection mid-infrared spectroscopy (ATR-MIR) and ultra-violet visible (UV-Vis) spectroscopy. The reference values were obtained by an official test panel. More details might be found in the paper by Borràs et al.²

The primary motivation of the author to participate in this challenge even though he is not joining the CAC 2026 was the similarity to his own research, detecting mycotoxin contamination by means of IR spectroscopy. Usually the data sets are imbalanced, the effect is small and the data are noisy.³ Yet the problem is of broad interest.⁴ This is also true for detecting sensory defects in olive oil by means of chemical analysis.²

The secondary motivation of joining the CAC 2026 data challenge was to explore the use of support vector machines (SVM) for complex classification problems. So far, the author only used partial least square discriminant analysis. This report was written before the predictions were submitted for the challenge and serves the purpose of summarizing the rationale behind the chosen modeling approach, but also to increase modeling transparency. No matter the outcome, the author would like to thank the organizers of this challenge.

Modeling strategy

As mentioned above it was decided to use SVM, for familiarization with this machine learning method, but also because it can handle non-linearities with reasonable computing times. The author had no experience with SVM nor data fusion, yet he was aware that SVMs suffer from high-dimensional data. It was thus decided to use principal component analysis (PCA) for dimension reduction, after data processing on the individual data blocks. The entire modelling pipeline was implemented in R 4.4.0 using Rstudio. The packages readxl,⁵ dplyr,⁶ mdatools,⁷ prospectr,⁸ dbscan,⁹ baseline¹⁰ and e1071¹¹ were employed.

For the UV-Vis spectra only the range from 600 - 800 nm was kept, as the range below 600 nm showed noise and extreme absorption, the region above 800 nm was removed as it belongs to the near-infrared (NIR) region. It was hypothesized that sensory panel assessments may be influenced by visual cues, thus colour might be more important than chemical composition found in the NIR region. Following the truncation, asymmetric least square (ALS) baseline correction was done, followed by a second order gap derivative and standard normal variate (SNV) correction. After that a trend between the two classes was observed in the scores. Due to the lack of experience of the author with HS-MS data, it was decided to guide the data handling strategy based on a discussion with the chat bot Copilot from Microsoft. First row normalization was used followed by variance filtering. The top 30% of the most variable variables were kept. Copilot also suggested other transformations, yet only with these settings in the score plot of the PCA a trend was observed. The author initially expected that the MIR spectra would show a

stronger correlation with the classes than the UV-Vis spectra. However, after testing multiple spectral preprocessing approaches, no clear trend emerged. It is possible that other factors obscure the information related to mustiness, as the data appear to exhibit some clustering that is not associated with the classification problem. Even though no clear trend was observed, it was decided to use ALS baseline correction followed by SNV to at least explore the influence during SVM modelling. The processed data and the score plots are shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1 Processed data and corresponding principal component analysis score plots.

Following data processing, outliers were removed. For this purpose, the local outlier factor (LOF) was calculated for each individual data block. The score and orthogonal distances from PCA models (cumvar = 95%) were used to guide parameter selection for LOF-based outlier detection. In total, 66 outliers were removed from the MIR data, and 22 each from the UV-Vis and HS-MS datasets.

After outlier removal, the remaining data were averaged at the sample level. Prior to SVM modelling, repeated random resampling of the dataset (80%, $n = 100$) was performed to determine the number of principal components (PCs) to retain. Based on this analysis, the first three PCs from the UV data and six PCs from the HS-MS data were selected. The corresponding scores were concatenated and used for SVM hyperparameter optimization via nested (double) cross-validation.

In this repeated validation framework, the processed and averaged dataset was split into an 80:20 ratio in the outer loop, ensuring that the proportion of musty (M) and non-musty (NM) samples was preserved to account for class imbalance. PCA was performed on the training set, and the test set was subsequently projected using the same PCA models. In the inner loop, 10-fold random cross-validation was applied.

The SVM hyperparameter search space included cost (C) values of 1, 5, and 10, and gamma (γ) values of 0.001, 0.01, and 0.05. To address class imbalance, class weighting was incorporated during training. Model performance was evaluated using the F1 score. Among the 100 tuned SVM models, 37 selected a γ of 0.01 and a C of 5, yielding an average F1 score of 0.76. The final model

was further assessed using repeated resampling. The results of SVM tuning and the performance of the final model are summarized in Figure 2.

A: SVM tuning results

cost	gamma	count	F1_mean
1	0.01	7	0.71
1	0.05	17	0.74
1	0.1	1	0.71
5	0.001	4	0.62
5	0.01	37	0.76
5	0.05	2	0.69
5	0.1	1	0.64
10	0.001	8	0.73
10	0.01	20	0.75
10	0.1	3	0.62

B: Final SVM model performance

Figure 2. Results of the hyperparameter search and histogram of the performance of the final model during resampling of the entire training set.

The test set to be predicted was processed as the training set, the replicates were averaged and transformed using the PCA established on the training set. Then the SVM model established on the training set was used for classification.

R-code

The entire workflow was divided into the snippets below. The data was imported like this:

```
pacman::p_load(readxl)
{path<-"directory of your choice /CAC2026_Data_challenge.xlsx"}
sheets <- excel_sheets(path)
df<-lapply(excel_sheets(path), read_excel, path = path)
names(df)<-sheets
list2env(df, .GlobalEnv)
Ref<-`CAL Reference values`
}
```

Then data processing and fusion was carried out.

```
pacman::p_load(dplyr,mdatools,prospectr,dbscan,baseline)

MIR<-`CAL ATR-FTIR`
UV<-`CAL UV-Vis`
HS<-`CAL HS-MS`
names(MIR)[1]<-"ID"
names(UV)[1]<-"ID"
names(HS)[1]<-"ID"

{#MIR outlier search
M<-MIR[,-1]
M <- M[, ! (as.numeric(colnames(M)) >= 1500 &
as.numeric(colnames(M)) <= 1700)]
B<-baseline(as.matrix(M), method = "als",lambda = 6,p = 0.01)
M<-getCorrected(B)
M<-standardNormalVariate(M)

M <- M[, ! (as.numeric(colnames(M)) >= 1500 &
as.numeric(colnames(M)) <= 1700)]

lof_scores <- lof(M, minPts = 30)
threshold <- quantile(lof_scores, 0.90)
Moutlier <- which(lof_scores > threshold)

#UV outlier search
UV<-`CAL UV-Vis`
names(UV)[1]<-"ID"
U<-UV[,-1]
w1 <- as.numeric(colnames(U))
U <- U[, w1 >= 600 & w1<= 800 ]
B<-baseline(as.matrix(U), method = "als",lambda = 6,p = 0.01)
U<-getCorrected(B)
U <- gapDer(U, m = 2, w =5 , s = 5)
U<-standardNormalVariate(U)
lof_scores <- lof(U, minPts = 20)
threshold <- quantile(lof_scores, 0.95)
Uoutlier <- which(lof_scores > threshold)

#HS outlier search
```

```

H<-HS[,-1]
H <- sweep(H, 1, rowSums(H, na.rm=TRUE), "/")
vars <- apply(H, 2, var)
keepH <- vars > quantile(vars, 0.7)
table(keepH)
H <- H[, keepH]
lof_scores <- lof(H, minPts = 15)
threshold <- quantile(lof_scores, 0.95)
Houtlier <- which(lof_scores > threshold)
}
MIR<-data.frame(ID = MIR$ID, M)
HS<-data.frame(ID = HS$ID, H)
UV<-data.frame(ID = UV$ID, U)
MIR<-MIR[-Houtlier,]
UV<-UV[-Houtlier,]
HS<-HS[-Houtlier,]

MIR <- MIR %>%
  group_by(ID) %>%
  summarise(across(where(is.numeric), mean, na.rm = TRUE))
UV <- UV %>%
  group_by(ID) %>%
  summarise(across(where(is.numeric), mean, na.rm = TRUE))
HS<- HS %>%
  group_by(ID) %>%
  summarise(across(where(is.numeric), mean, na.rm = TRUE))

keep<-Reduce(intersect, list(MIR$ID,UV$ID,HS$ID))

MIR <- MIR[MIR$ID %in% keep, ]
UV <- UV[UV$ID %in% keep, ]
HS <- HS[HS$ID %in% keep, ]
MIR <- MIR[order(MIR$ID), ]
UV <- UV[order(UV$ID), ]
HS <- HS[order(HS$ID), ]
identical(MIR$ID, UV$ID)
identical(MIR$ID, HS$ID)

Class<-Ref$Musty[match(MIR$ID, Ref$Sample)]
Class <- as.factor(ifelse(Class == 0, "NM", "M"))

matplot(as.numeric(colnames(U)),
        t(U),
        xlab = "Wavelength / nm",
        type = "l",
        ylab = "a.u.",
        main = "")
title(main = "A: Processed UV-Vis spectra", adj = 0)
PCA_U<-pca(UV[,-1],scale = F,center=T,ncomp=20)
plotScores(PCA_U,cgroup=factor(Class),main="")
title(main = "D:UV-Vis PCA scores", adj = 0)

matplot(as.numeric(colnames(M)),
        t(M),
        xlab = "Wavenumber / cm-1",
        type = "l",
        ylab = "a.u.",
        main = "", # suppress default centered title
        xlim = rev(range(as.numeric(colnames(M)))))
title(main = "B: Processed ATR-MIR spectra", adj = 0)

PCA_M<-pca(MIR[,-1],scale = F,center=T,ncomp=20)
plotScores(PCA_M,cgroup=factor(Class),main="")
title(main = "E: MIR PCA scores", adj = 0)

matplot(as.numeric(colnames(H)),
        t(H),
        xlab = "m/z",
        type = "l",
        ylab = "a.u.",
        main = "")
title(main = "C: Processed HS-MS spectra", adj = 0)
PCA_H<-pca(HS[,-1],scale = F,center=T,ncomp=20)
plotScores(PCA_H,cgroup=factor(Class),main="")
title(main = "F: HS-MS PCA scores", adj = 0)

```

Searching for the number of PCs:

```

pacman::p_load(mdatools)
set.seed(123)
n <- 100
ncomp <- numeric(n)
split <- logical(n)
for (i in 1:n) {

  trainM <- sample(which(Class=="M"), 0.8 * sum(Class=="M"))
  trainN <- sample(which(Class=="NM"), 0.8 * sum(Class=="NM"))
  train <- c(trainM, trainN)

  Mc <- MIR[train, -1]
  Mv <- MIR[-train,-1]

  PCA <- pca(Mc, scale = F, center = TRUE, ncomp = 50, x.test = Mv)

  cumvarC <- cumsum(PCA$calres$expvar)
  ncompC <- which(cumvarC >= 95)[1]

  ncomp[i] <- ncompC

  # Optional: check projection stability
  cumvarV <- cumsum(PCA$res$test$expvar)
  ncompV <- which(cumvarV >= 95)[1]
  split[i] <- (ncompC == ncompV)
}

```

```
table(ncomp)
```

SVM hyperparameter search:

Computing time 2 minutes 48 seconds on an Lenovo Desktop i5 10500 @ 3.10 Ghz 16 GB.

```
pacman::p_load(mdatools,e1071)

set.seed(123)
n<-100
res<-data.frame(matrix(nrow=n,ncol=6))
names(res)<-c("cost","gamma","performance","precision","recall","F1")
set.seed(123)
system.time(for (i in 1:n) {

  trainM<-sample(which(Class=="M"),length(which(Class=="M"))*0.8)
  trainN<-sample(which(Class=="NM"),length(which(Class=="NM"))*0.8)
  train<-c(trainM,trainN)

  Mc<-MIR[train,-1]
  Mv<-MIR[-train,-1]
  Uc<-UV[train,-1]
  Uv<-UV[-train,-1]
  Hc<-HS[train,-1]
  Hv<-HS[-train,-1]

  #ncomp were searched previously
  PCA_M<-pca(Mc,scale = F,center=T,ncomp=10,x.test=Mv)
  PCA_U<-pca(Uc,scale = F,center=T,ncomp=10,x.test=Uv)
  PCA_H<-pca(Hc,scale = F,center=T,ncomp=10,x.test=Hv)

  SMC <- PCA_M$calres$scores[,1:6]
  SMV <- PCA_M$res$test$scores[,1:6]
  SUC <- PCA_U$calres$scores[,1:3]
  SUV <- PCA_U$res$test$scores[,1:3]
  SHC <- PCA_H$calres$scores[,1:6]
  SHV <- PCA_H$res$test$scores[,1:6]

  # Class labels
  Cc <- Class[train]
  Cv <- Class[-train]

  #concatenate scores

  Xc <- cbind( SUC ,SHC)
  Xv <- cbind( SUV ,SHV)
  Xc_scaled <- scale(Xc)

  # Apply scaling to test data
  Xv_scaled <- scale(Xv,
                    center = attr(Xc_scaled, "scaled:center"),
                    scale = attr(Xc_scaled, "scaled:scale"))

  tempc <- data.frame(Class = Cc, Xc_scaled)
  tempv <- data.frame(Class = Cv, Xv_scaled)

  obj <- tune.svm(
    Class ~ .,
    data = tempc,
    type = "C-classification",
    class.weights = c(M = 2, NM = 1),
    kernel="radial",
    cost = c(1, 5,10),
    gamma = c(0.001,0.01, 0.05, 0.1,1),
    tunecontrol = tune.control(sampling = "cross",cross=10),
    scale=F
  )

  pred <- predict(obj$best.model, tempv[,,-1])
  true <- Cv

  TP <- sum(pred == "M" & true == "M")
  FP <- sum(pred == "M" & true != "M")
  FN <- sum(pred != "M" & true == "M")

  precision <- TP / (TP + FP)
  recall <- TP / (TP + FN)
  f1 <- 2 * precision * recall / (precision + recall)

  res[i,1]<-obj$best.model$cost
  res[i,2]<-obj$best.model$gamma
  res[i,3]<-obj$best.performance
  res$precision[i]<-precision
  res$recall[i]<-recall
  res$F1[i]<-f1
})

table(res$cost, res$gamma)
aggregate(F1 ~ cost + gamma, data = res, function(x) c(mean = mean(x), count = length(x)))
```

Testing the final model:

```
pacman::p_load(mdatools,e1071)

set.seed(123)
n<-100
res<-data.frame(matrix(nrow=n,ncol=6))
names(res)<-c("cost","gamma","precision","recall","F1")
```

```

set.seed(123)
for (i in 1:n) {

  trainM<-sample(which(Class=="M"),length(which(Class=="M"))*0.8)
  trainN<-sample(which(Class=="NM"),length(which(Class=="NM"))*0.8)
  train<-c(trainM,trainN)

  Mc<-MIR[train,-1]
  Mv<-MIR[-train,-1]
  Uc<-UV[train,-1]
  Uv<-UV[-train,-1]
  Hc<-HS[train,-1]
  Hv<-HS[-train,-1]

  #ncomp were searched previously
  PCA_M<-pca(Mc,scale = F,center=T,ncomp=10,x.test=Mv)
  PCA_U<-pca(Uc,scale = F,center=T,ncomp=10,x.test=Uv)
  PCA_H<-pca(Hc,scale = F,center=T,ncomp=20,x.test=Hv)

  SMC <- PCA_M$calres$scores[,1:5]
  SMV <- PCA_M$res$test$scores[,1:5]
  SUC <- PCA_U$calres$scores[,1:3]
  SUV <- PCA_U$res$test$scores[,1:3]
  SHC <- PCA_H$calres$scores[,1:6]
  SHV <- PCA_H$res$test$scores[,1:6]

  # Class labels
  Cc <- Class[train]
  Cv <- Class[-train]

  # Concatenate scores

  Xc <- cbind(SUC,SHC)
  Xv <- cbind(SUV,SHV)
  Xc_scaled <- scale(Xc)

  # Apply scaling to test data
  Xv_scaled <- scale(Xv,
                    center = attr(Xc_scaled, "scaled:center"),
                    scale = attr(Xc_scaled, "scaled:scale"))
  tempc <- data.frame(Class = Cc, Xc_scaled)
  tempv <- data.frame(Class = Cv, Xv_scaled)

  model <- svm(
    Class ~ .,
    data = tempc,
    type = "C-classification",
    class.weights = c(M = 2, NM = 1),
    kernel = "radial",
    cost = 5,
    gamma = 0.01,
    scale = F
  )

  pred <- predict(model, tempv[,-1])
  true <- Cv

  TP <- sum(pred == "M" & true == "M")
  FP <- sum(pred == "M" & true != "M")
  FN <- sum(pred != "M" & true == "M")

  precision <- TP / (TP + FP)
  recall <- TP / (TP + FN)
  f1 <- 2 * precision * recall / (precision + recall)

  res[i,1]<-model$cost
  res[i,2]<-model$gamma
  res$precision[i]<-precision
  res$recall[i]<-recall
  res$F1[i]<-f1
}
hist(res$F1, xlab="F1-score", main = "Histogramm of final SVM model")

```

Predict the unknown data:

```

UVT<-`TEST UV-Vis`
HST<-`TEST HS-MS`

names(UVT)[1]<-"ID"
names(HST)[1]<-"ID"
UT<-UVT[,-1]
w1 <- as.numeric(colnames(UT))
UT <- UT[, w1 >= 600 & w1<= 800 ]
B<-baseline(as.matrix(UT), method = "als",lambda = 6,p = 0.01)
UT<-getCorrected(B)
UT <- gapDer(UT, m = 2, w =5 , s = 5)
UT<-standardNormalVariate(UT)

HT<-HST[,-1]
HT <- sweep(HT, 1, rowSums(HT, na.rm=TRUE), "/")
HT <- HT[, keepH]

matplot(as.numeric(colnames(HT)),
        t(HT),
        xlab="Wavelength",
        type = "l",
        ylab="a.u.")
HST<-data.frame(ID = HST$ID, HT)
UVT<-data.frame(ID = UVT$ID, UT)

```

```

UVT <- UVT %>%
  group_by(ID) %>%
  summarise(across(where(is.numeric), mean, na.rm = TRUE))
HST<- HST %>%
  group_by(ID) %>%
  summarise(across(where(is.numeric), mean, na.rm = TRUE))
PCA_U<-pca(UV[, -1], scale = F, center=T, ncomp=20, x.test = UVT[-1])
plotScores(PCA_U, main="UV PCA scores")
PCA_H<-pca(HS[, -1], scale = F, center=T, ncomp=20, x.test=HST[, -1])
plotScores(PCA_H, main="HS-MS PCA scores")
plot(PCA_H)
SUC <- PCA_U$calres$scores[,1:3]
SUT <- PCA_U$res$test$scores[,1:3]
SHC <- PCA_H$calres$scores[,1:6]
SHT <- PCA_H$res$test$scores[,1:6]

Xc <- cbind(SUC, SHC)
Xt <- cbind(SUT, SHT)

Xc<- scale(Xc)

# Apply scaling to test data
Xt <- scale(Xt,
            center = attr(Xc_scaled, "scaled:center"),
            scale = attr(Xc_scaled, "scaled:scale"))

# Put back into data frames
Xc <- data.frame(Class, Xc)
Xt <- data.frame(Xt)

model <- svm(
  Class ~ .,
  data = Xc,
  type = "C-classification",
  class.weights = c(M = 2, NM = 1),
  kernel = "radial",
  cost = 5,
  gamma = 0.01,
  scale = F
)

pred_test <- predict(model, Xt)

results<-data.frame(ID = HST$ID, pred_test)
results

```

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